

IN-SITU OBSERVATION AND MODELLING OF MICROMECHANICAL FAILURE PROCESS IN CFRP CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The microscopic failure process of cross-ply laminates, (0/90_n/0) (n=4, 8, 12), was investigated at R.T. and 80°C for conventional T300/3601 and toughened-type T800H/3631 carbon/epoxy composites. *In-situ* observation of microscopic failure process was conducted using an optical microscope (OM), a scanning acoustic microscope (SAM) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) with "instrumented loading devices", as well as replica technique. Progressive damage parameters such as transverse crack density and total delamination length were measured as a function of strain. Thermal residual strains were measured by "ply separation method". Then, shear-lag analysis including thermal residual strains was conducted to obtain a new theoretical prediction of transverse crack density as a function of laminate strain considering constraint effect. This new model considered statistical 90° ply strength and predicted the experimentally-obtained progressive damages. Furthermore, the analysis was extended to the system containing delaminations which initiate from transverse cracks.

Keywords: CFRP, Cross-Ply Laminates, Delamination, Microscopic Failure Process, Temperature Effect, Transverse Crack

1. INTRODUCTION

In many applications of fiber reinforced plastics, fibers are aligned in more than one direction to provide high load-bearing capability. Among these composites, cross-ply laminates have been extensively studied because this is a basic laminate configuration [1-14].

Garrett, Bailey and Parvizi [1-3] discussed failure behavior of cross-ply laminates in the view of strength and energy concept. They derived the relation between transverse crack spacing and laminate strain, considering the stress redistribution in 90° ply using one-dimensional shear-lag analysis. They also showed that transverse crack onset strain increases as the thickness of 90° ply decreases, which was called 'constraint effect'. This onset strain was derived from the energy concept.

Fukunaga et al. [4] conducted stress analysis using modified shear-lag analysis considering the interlaminar shear layer. The analysis takes the thermal residual stresses and Poisson effect into account. They derived the relation between transverse crack spacing and applied laminate stress considering statistical characteristics of 90° ply strength. Such theoretical predictions of transverse crack density were also conducted by Wang et al. [5,6] (simulation based on fracture mechanics), Laws and Dvorak [7], Han et al. [8] (shear-lag analysis and energy criterion), Lee and Daniel [9] (shear-lag analysis and strength criterion), and Nairn [10] (variational approach and energy criterion). Peters [11,12] considered 90° ply as a chain of elements that breaks only once until ultimate fracture of the laminate, and expressed the statistical strength of the elements as Weibull distribution. The relation between the statistical parameters and materials properties were discussed. Lim and Hong [13,14] modified the boundary conditions of Fukunaga et al.'s [4] shear-lag analysis and discussed the effect of crack density on mechanical and thermal properties of cross-ply

laminates. These previous studies, however, provide few *in-situ* microscopic experimental data to support their predictions.

In the present work, the effects of temperature on the fracture process and mechanisms of CFRP cross-ply laminates are investigated microscopically. Progressive damage parameters such as transverse crack density and total delamination length are measured at R.T. and 80°C. Then, comparison of models (strength and energy criterion based on shear-lag analysis) that predict transverse crack density as a function of applied laminate strain is conducted based on above data. Thermal residual strain in 90° ply is measured by "ply separation method", based on the measurement of the curvature of unsymmetric laminate beam. A model which considers the strength distribution of 90° ply strength, thermal residual strain and constraint effect is proposed to predict the transverse crack density. In addition, modified shear-lag analysis is extended to the system including delamination at the tips of transverse cracks, and the critical energy release rate for delamination onset is estimated which is only possible with the accurate observation of *in-situ* failure process.

2. EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Materials

Three different cross-ply stacking sequences, (0/90_n/0) (n=4,8,12) were used for both conventional T300/3601 and toughened-type T800H/3631 composite systems. Fiber volume fraction was about 60%. Both T300 and T800H are high strength carbon fibers, but the latter has higher modulus, strength, and failure strain. The 3601 is a TGDDM/DDS epoxy system, but the 3631 is a modified epoxy system for toughness improvement.

2.2. Tensile Tests and Observation of Failure Process

Tensile tests were performed at R.T. (20°C) and at 80°C. *In-situ* observation of microscopic failure process was conducted using OM, SAM (Olympus UH-3) and SEM (Hitachi S-2150) with "instrumented tensile loading devices" on their respective stages. Furthermore, the replica technique was also used during tensile tests. The polished edge surface of a specimen was replicated on the replica film (acetyl cellulose film) with methyl acetate as solvent. Damage state in large area at each strain level can be preserved after tests using this technique. The distributions of tensile transverse strength of UD of each system at R.T. and 80°C were also obtained to predict the failure progress properties of 90° ply in cross-ply laminates. About 20 specimens were tested under each condition.

2.3. Measurement of Thermal Residual Strain by Ply Separation Method

Thermal residual strains occur when laminates are cooled down from cured temperature to service temperature because of difference in thermal expansion coefficients of 0° ply and 90° ply. In 90° ply, tensile thermal residual strain is generated due to its larger thermal expansion coefficient than 0° ply. Accurate evaluation of the residual strain is not easy. However, assuming that thermal expansion coefficient is constant with temperature and that each ply deforms uniformly, thermal residual strain in 90° ply, ϵ_2^T , is shown to be (based on classical lamination theory) [3]

$$\epsilon_2^T = -\frac{bE_1(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)}{bE_1 + dE_2} \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is temperature difference ($=T_2 - T_1$, T_2 ; test temperature, T_1 ; cured temperature). b and d are thickness of 0° ply and half thickness of 90° ply. E and α denote Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient. Subscripts 1 and 2 represent 0° and 90° ply, respectively.

It is not easy to measure accurately thermal expansion coefficients, which vary with temperature. To overcome these problems, there is a method to calculate thermal residual strains using unsymmetric 0°/90° laminates [15, 16]. For cylindrical thermal deformation of a bimaterial strip, Timoshenko [17] has shown that

$$-(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)\Delta T = \frac{h_1 + h_2}{2R} + \frac{h_1^3 E_1 + h_2^3 E_2}{6R(h_1 + h_2)} \left(\frac{1}{E_1 h_1} + \frac{1}{E_2 h_2} \right) \quad (2)$$

where h_1 and h_2 are thicknesses of 0° and 90° plies in an unsymmetric laminate, respectively, and R is radius of curvature of the laminate. Substituting equation 2 into equation 1 and measuring the radius of curvature of the unsymmetric laminate, thermal residual strain in 90° ply, ϵ_2^T , can be obtained.

In this study, unsymmetric laminates were made by grinding 0° ply of one side in (0/90₈/0) of each composite system and the radius of curvature was measured at R.T. and 80°C. This method is called "ply separation method" in the present study. No damage by grinding was observed to affect the curvature of the laminates. Following ref. [16], the curved unsymmetric laminates were assumed to form a part of circumference of a circle. In this study, analysis was carried out using not only the thermal residual strains obtained by ply separation method, but those calculated by equation 1 using catalog data of thermal expansion coefficients for comparison.

2.4. Shear-Lag Analysis and Failure Criteria

The modified shear-lag analysis considering interlaminar shear layer was first conducted by Fukunaga et al. [4]. The boundary condition of the method was modified by Lim and Hong [13,14] to satisfy arbitrary crack spacings. In this study, the stress state in a cross-ply laminate was calculated following their method. For simplicity, the method was reduced to one dimensional.

2.4.1. Transverse Cracking Criterion

1) Stress criterion

Using a stress criterion, transverse cracks occur when 90° ply stress σ_2 reaches its strength σ_{2B} . Following ref. [1], it is assumed that the first transverse crack occurs at the middle point of the specimen, and that next transverse cracks occur at the middle point between the existing cracks. Then 2ⁿ cracks occur[18] at laminate strain ϵ_0 satisfying (L_s ; specimen length)

$$E_2(\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_2^T) \left[1 - \left\{ \frac{2}{\exp(\xi \frac{L_s}{2^n}) + \exp(-\xi \frac{L_s}{2^n})} \right\} \right] = \sigma_{2B} \quad (3)$$

2) Energy criterion

Using the concept of energy balance [3] and assuming all the crack spacings are equal, 2ⁿ cracks can be shown to occur[18] at laminate strain ϵ_0 satisfying

$$G_{tc} = \frac{E_2(bE_1 + dE_2)}{2bE_1\xi} (\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_2^T)^2 \left[2 \tanh(\xi \frac{L_s}{2^{n+1}}) - \tanh(\xi \frac{L_s}{2^n}) \right] \quad (4)$$

where G_{tc} is the critical energy release rate for transverse cracking.

2.4.2. Extension of Shear-Lag Analysis[18]

Here, we consider the state that delamination with length of $2a$ has developed at each tip of transverse cracks (crack spacing is $2L$). Assuming that there is no friction between 0° and 90° plies in the delaminated region, all stress components in 90° are zero in the region. For simplicity, we assume that each delamination grows with the same rate at a constant load. Following a similar procedure to the derivation of energy release rate for transverse cracking, energy release rate associated with the delamination growth G_d is obtained as a function of crack spacing $2L$ and delamination length $2a$,

$$G_d = \frac{dE_2(E_1b + E_2d)(\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_2^T)^2}{2bE_1} \left\{ 1 - \frac{4}{[\exp\{\xi(L-a)\} - \exp\{-\xi(L-a)\}]^2} \right\} \quad (5)$$

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Tensile Tests and *In-Situ* Observation of Failure Process

Temperature dependence of the ultimate strength of each cross-ply laminate is rather small because the ultimate strength mainly depends on the 0° ply strength. However, temperature dependence of microscopic damage development process is different as will be shown later.

Figure 1 shows a transverse crack which is a type of damage first observed in each laminate (T300/3601 (0/90₄/0), R.T., $\epsilon_0=0.94\%$, SAM, 400MHz). These transverse cracks run through the thickness of 90° ply and stop at the 0°/90° interface.

Figures 2 and 3 show transverse crack density as a function of applied laminate strain for T800H/3631 and T300/3601 systems, respectively. The transverse crack density is defined as the number of cracks per unit specimen length. In T800H/3631 system, the crack density decreases and

the first cracking strain increases at 80°C. On the other hand, in T300/3601 system, the crack density is relatively high at 80°C, and the temperature dependence of first cracking strain is small. In T300/3601 (0/90₁₂/0) laminate, first cracking strain and ultimate laminate strain are comparable and progressive crack multiplication was not observed. In both systems, first cracking strain is about the same or larger than 90° UD ultimate strain. This is due to the constraint effect [3]. Figure 4 shows SAM images (pulse-wave mode, high NA lens, 30MHz, Olympus) of 0°/90° interface of T800H/3631 (0/90₈/0). Transverse cracks running thorough the width of the specimen and crack multiplication are clearly observed.

At higher strain level, delamination at the tips of transverse cracks is observed in T800H/3631 system. Figure 5 shows progressive delamination growth in T800H/3631 (0/90₈/0). In this system, delamination grows gradually and to a large extent before final fracture. In T300/3601 system, on the contrary, delamination was not observed in macroscopic level. Figure 6 shows SEM images of the delamination tips. In T800H/3631 system, delamination propagates as fiber/matrix interfacial debonding. In T300/3601 system, microscopic delamination as shear fracture of matrix is observed which implies good adhesion between fiber and matrix. Figure 7 shows total delamination length (sum of the delamination length in the specimen) as a function of applied laminate strain for T800H/3631 system. The temperature dependence of delamination is similar to that of transverse crack. And for thicker 90° ply, delamination grows rapidly and extensively.

3.2. Strength Distribution of 90° UD

The strength distribution of 90° UD (volume V_s) is assumed to obey a two-parameter Weibull distribution. The probability distribution function is

$$F_s(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left\{ -V_s \left(\frac{\sigma}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right\} \quad (6)$$

where β is shape parameter and α is a parameter that corresponds to scale parameter. The parameters for each system at each temperature obtained by Weibull plotting are shown in Table 1. The scatter in strength is smaller at 80°C than at R.T. for both systems.

Table 1. Weibull parameters of CFRP (90₁₅) laminate strength distribution

($V_s=6.0 \times 10^{-9}(\text{m}^3)$, n; the number of specimens tested)

		α	β	
T800H/3631	R.T.	8.69	7.69	(n=18)
	80°C	11.8	9.36	(n=18)
T300/3601	R.T.	5.13	6.50	(n=20)
	80°C	10.1	9.46	(n=19)

3.3. Thermal Residual Strain in 90° Ply

The residual thermal strains in 90° ply obtained by 'ply separation method' (PSM) and by classical lamination theory (CLT) using catalog data of constant thermal expansion coefficient are compared in Table 2. A large difference is seen between $(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$ and $(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$. It implies that quantitative estimation of thermal residual strain is important.

Table 2. Thermal residual strain in 90° ply

Laminate	$(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$ (%)		$(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$ (%)	
	R.T.	80°C	R.T.	80°C
T800H/3631	($\alpha_1=0.10 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, $\alpha_2=35.5 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)			
(0/90 ₄ /0)	0.252	0.167	0.503	0.318
(0/90 ₈ /0)	0.226	0.152	0.454	0.289
(0/90 ₁₂ /0)	0.206	0.139	0.323	0.265
T300/3601	($\alpha_1=-0.40 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$, $\alpha_2=30.0 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$)			
(0/90 ₄ /0)	0.211	0.122	0.427	0.271
(0/90 ₈ /0)	0.188	0.110	0.381	0.243
(0/90 ₁₂ /0)	0.170	0.100	0.342	0.221

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Prediction of Transverse Crack Density (Part 1: Deterministic Approach)

The predictions of transverse cracking by strength criterion and energy criterion with experimental results are compared in Figures 2 and 3. In the strength criterion, 90° ply strength is assumed to be equal to average 90° UD strength. In the energy criterion, the critical energy release rate G_{1c} is determined from first cracking strain, ϵ_0^{fpf} , of (0/90₄/0) for both systems. The critical energy release rate G_{1c} are shown in Table 3. Figures 2 and 3 show comparison of predictions and experimental results. For strength criterion, predictions are made using both $(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$ and $(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$. For energy criterion, prediction is shown for only $(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$ because effect of thermal residual strain is small. In strength criterion, the prediction of both first cracking strain and multiplication of transverse cracks are poor. In energy criterion, first cracking strain is in good agreement. However, it predicts rapid crack multiplication as laminate strain increases. These are similar results to Han et al.'s [8] and they pointed out that the critical energy release rate for transverse cracking is an increasing function of crack density. In this study, a more reasonable model predicting transverse crack density is proposed through probabilistic approach in the next section.

Table 3. Critical energy release rate for transverse cracking G_{1c} (J/m²)

Material		T800H/3631	T300/3601
R.T	$(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$	146	148
	$(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$	94.8 ($\epsilon_0^{fpf}=0.80\%$)	107 ($\epsilon_0^{fpf}=0.95\%$)
80°C	$(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$	155	97.4
	$(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$	125 ($\epsilon_0^{fpf}=1.15\%$)	75.9 ($\epsilon_0^{fpf}=1.00\%$)

4.2. Prediction of Transverse Crack Density (Part 2: Probabilistic Approach)

A model predicting relationship between applied laminate strain and transverse crack density is presented using statistical parameters of experimentally obtained 90° UD strength distribution. Similar to Peters et al. [11,12], 90° ply in cross-ply laminate is divided into elements which can fail once up to the ultimate failure. The strength distribution of the elements can be assumed by the distribution of transverse strength of UD. Then, failure probability of the elements under a stress is known and the number of cracks can be calculated by multiplying the number of elements.

The length of an element is determined from shear-lag analysis. Twice of x that satisfies $\sigma_2/\sigma_{20} = 0.8$ is determined as element length L_e . Assuming α and β are independent of volume, the strength distribution of the element (volume V_e) is

$$F_e(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left\{ -V_e \left(\frac{\sigma}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right\} \quad (7)$$

The number of elements m in the specimen with length L_s is L_s/L_e . When 90° ply stress is σ_2 , the number of cracks is $mF_e(\sigma_2)$. Here, constraint effect [3] is taken into account. The difference between $(\epsilon_0^{fpf})^{ene}$ (first cracking strain predicted by energy criterion) and $(\epsilon_0^{fpf})^{str}$ (first cracking strain predicted by strength criterion)

$$\epsilon_c = (\epsilon_0^{fpf})^{ene} - (\epsilon_0^{fpf})^{str} \quad (8)$$

is defined as constraint strain and it is introduced as location parameter of Weibull distribution. Consequently, transverse crack density ρ is expressed as a function of laminate strain by [18]

$$\rho = \frac{1}{L_e} \left[1 - \exp \left\{ -V_e \left(\frac{E_2(\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_2^T - \epsilon_c)}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right\} \right] \quad (9)$$

Figures 2 and 3 show comparison of the predictions by the present probabilistic approach with experimental results, and they are in good agreement, which proves the validity of the present model.

4.3. Delamination Behavior

In Sec. 2.4.2., the energy release rate for delamination is obtained as a function of transverse crack spacing and delamination length by extending shear-lag analysis. The critical energy release rate for delamination onset G_{dc} can be determined, setting delamination length $a=0$ in equation 5, and measuring crack spacing $2L$ and laminate strain ϵ_0 at delamination onset by *in-situ* observation.

The experimentally obtained energy release rate for delamination onset using both $(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$ and $(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$ are shown in Table 4. G_{dc} using $(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$ is larger because the total 90° ply strain is larger. G_{dc} for (0/90₄/0) and (0/90₈/0) is about the same although G_{dc} for (0/90₈/0) is slightly higher. The G_{dc} value ranging 340-380J/m² is a reasonable one, compared with the experimentally obtained Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. In the case of (0/90₁₂/0), however, G_{dc} is much larger than that of other laminates. This is because the first cracking strain is higher than the delamination onset strain theoretically expected if we assume G_{dc} is equal to that of other laminates. In (0/90₁₂/0) laminate, delamination occurs at first cracking strain. An attempt is being made to predict delamination growth as a function of laminate strain.

Table 4.. Critical energy release rate for delamination onset G_{dc}
for T800H/3631 (0/90_n/0) (J/m²)

Laminate	(0/90 ₄ /0)	(0/90 ₈ /0)	(0/90 ₁₂ /0)
R.T. $(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$	473	516	596
$(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$	364	380	507
80°C $(\epsilon_2^T)^{CLT}$	401	451	604
$(\epsilon_2^T)^{PSM}$	344	377	512

5. CONCLUSIONS

(1) *In-situ* observation of microscopic failure process of CFRP cross-ply laminates was conducted by OM, SAM and SEM with 'instrumented loading devices', as well as replica technique. Differences in the failure process due to material systems and temperature were investigated microscopically.

(2) A new probabilistic model predicting transverse cracking behavior was presented using experimentally obtained 90° UD strength distribution and thermal residual strains measured by 'ply separation method' and considering constraint effect. The present prediction showed good agreement with experimental results while the deterministic approach showed poor agreement.

(3) Modified shear-lag analysis was extended to the system including delamination at the tips of transverse cracks. And the critical energy release rate for delamination onset was successfully estimated which was only possible by the *in-situ* observation of damage progress conducted in this study.

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Figure 1. Transverse Crack in T300/3601 (0/90₄/0). R.T., $\epsilon_0=0.94\%$, SAM, 400MHz

Figure 4. SAM Images of 0°/90° Interface of T800H/3631 (0/90₈/0). (Pulse-Wave Mode, High NA Lens, 30MHz, Olympus). (a) $\epsilon_0=1.1\%$, (b) $\epsilon_0=1.5\%$

Figure 5. Delamination Growth at the Tip of a Transverse Crack in T800H/3631 (0/90₈/0). 80°C (Replica). (a) $\epsilon_0=0.97\%$, (b) $\epsilon_0=1.03\%$, (c) $\epsilon_0=1.09\%$

Figure 6. SEM Images of Delamination. (a) Fiber/Matrix Interfacial Debonding in T800H/3631 (0/90₄/0). ($\sigma_0=467\text{MPa}$) (b) Shear Fracture of Matrix Resin at the Tip of Microscopic Delamination in T300/3601 (0/90₄/0). ($\sigma_0=339\text{MPa}$)

Figure 2. Transverse Crack Density as a Function of Applied Laminate Strain for T800H/3631. (a) (0/904/0), (b) (0/908/0), (c) (0/9012/0). Experimental Results ● R.T. ○ 80°C Deterministic Approach; Strength Criterion $(\epsilon_{T_2})_{CLT}$ ▲ R.T. △ 80°C Strength Criterion $(\epsilon_{T_2})_{PSM}$ ■ R.T. □ 80°C, Energy Criterion ◆ R.T. ◇ 80°C Probabilistic Present Approach; — R.T. ---- 80°C

Figure 3. Transverse Crack Density as a Function of Applied Laminate Strain for T300/3601. (a) (0/904/0), (b) (0/908/0), (c) (0/9012/0).

Symbols and lines are the same as in Figure 2.

Figure 7. Total Delamination Length as a Function of Applied Laminate Strain for T800H/3631. (a) (0/904/0), (b) (0/908/0), (c) (0/9012/0). Experimental Results ● R.T. ○ 80°C